

ated at the ACRI experimental farm, Madurai, to determine population fluctuations and peak emergence of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason). The data will help scientists predict pest occurrence and insecticide applications.

The earliest gall midge capture was in the second week of Aug. Populations gradually increased until mid-Oct, then declined (see figure). Peak occurrence coincided with the maximum tillering phase of the rice crop. □

Adult midges collected in a bamboo light-trap with a 40-watt bulb, Madurai, India, 1981-82.

Insecticide toxicity to natural brown planthopper enemies

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We investigated contact toxicity of some foliar insecticides on brown planthopper predators: the mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter and spiders, *Lycosa* sp., that inhabit the rice ecosystem

Two 10-day-old TN1 seedlings were planted in clay pots. Plants were sprayed with insecticides 20 days after planting; 24 h later 10 adult mirid bugs (5 males and 5 females) were released per pot and confined in mylar cages. To prevent the predators from starving, three to four BPH nymphs were released in each pot.

Twenty spiderlings were forced to crawl over a chemical solution film in a

Toxicity of insecticides to brown planthopper predators.^a

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	<i>C. lividipennis</i>	<i>Lycosa</i> sp.
Decamethrin 0.002%	100 a	98 a
Methyl parathion 0.04%	100 a	98 a
Cypermethrin 0.002%	93 a	93 a
Fenvalerate 0.002%	93 a	92 a
Quinalphos 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Phosalone 0.04%	93 a	92 a
Permethrin 0.002%	92 a	90 a
Fenthion 0.04%	85 ab	90 a
Methamidophos 0.04%	76 b	87 ab
Phosphamidon 0.04%	76 b	79 b
FMC35001 0.04%	76 b	74 b

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b Analysis based on arcsin/percentage values. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

large petri dish for 2 min then immediately transferred to glass tubes which were covered with muslin. Predator mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Decamethrin and methyl parathion caused 100% *C. lividipennis* mortality,

closely followed by cypermethrin, fenvalerate, quinalphos, phosalone, and permethrin (see table). All insecticides tested were highly toxic to spiderlings. Mortality ranged from 74% (FMC35001) to 98% (decamethrin and methyl parathion). □

Pest management and control WEEDS

Sawdust-mulching for controlling weeds in transplanted summer rice

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Weeds are a major constraint to successful summer rice cultivation in Assam. Sawdust mulch 0, 2, and 4 cm thick was tested for weed control on Pusa 33, Mairang, and Ngoba in a split-plot design with 4 replications. On 25 Apr, 25-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 20 × 15 cm

Table 1. Fresh weight of weeds per 1.8 m² in rice fields with different sawdust mulching.

Variety	Fresh wt (g) of weeds			Mean ^a
	0	2-cm mulch	4-cm mulch	
Pusa 33	960	700	720	793.3 b
Mairang	2790	1466	853	1703.0 a
Ngoba	1100	1016	866	944.0 b
Mean ^a	1616.7 a	1060.7 b	873.0 c	

^a Any two means followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of probability.

spacing on 9-m² plots. At land preparation, 80 kg N, 21.5 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha were applied. Weed samples were col-

lected from 1.8-m² strips from each plot. Mulching significantly suppressed weed growth (Table 1). Weed weights